

Nanggroe: Jurnal Pengabdian Cendikia
Volume 3, Nomor 3, June 2024, Halaman 84-86
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ISSN: [2986-7002](https://doi.org/10.24054/nanggroe.v3i3.12567929)
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24054/nanggroe.v3i3.12567929>

Introduction To Body Parts Using English Learning Media

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Abstrak

The existence of the learning media nowadays is more developed in media technology as well as its delivery. Generally, learning media in elementary level is still using conventional method and focus on text only. Because of this condition, it is very important to have alternative media which is more interesting to be used, in this case, a learning media was proposed as the media for introducing parts of body for elementary students. For developing this application, parts of body could be introduced based on learning material in curriculum 2013. It was also developed by using Godfrey method. It can be significantly used for introducing parts of body in English for grade 1-2. It could be very helpful for the teachers or students where they don't only use lecture method but it can be use as one of alternative media. This 2D learning media was designed by using adobe flash CS6, Action Script 3. Based on the learning media testing, there are 89,41% who agreed that this application for English learning as the introduction for parts of body is easy to be used.

Keywords: *English Learning Media, Introducing parts of body*

Article Info

Received date: 25 May 2024

Revised date: 1 June 2024

Accepted date: 10 June 2024

INTRODUCTION

Current technological developments have a great influence on elementary school children's learning and the delivery of material delivered by teachers at school. At the elementary school age level, students prefer games and other entertainment, which can attract the child's attention. There are two components that can be used for the success of learning, namely learning methods and learning media, where the two components above are interrelated, so that they can be used as a vehicle for conveying information to elementary school students (Asra M, 2009). Apart from that, according to Andriani (2012) the learning method still uses the lecture method, taking notes and working on questions and the learning media delivered by the teacher is still limited, so it can be categorized as still conventional.

According to the Ministry of National Education in Decree of the Minister of National Education No. 22 of 2006 English is a tool for communicating verbally and in writing. Communicating is understanding and expressing information, thoughts, feelings, and developing science, technology and culture using this language. English subjects are given to students starting from elementary school to train students so they are able to speak foreign languages. Apart from that, the era of globalization and current developments requires elementary school students to stay up to date with English learning materials. As is the case at SD 004, Batam City, which has been provided with English subjects starting from grade 1, even though it is still included in local content, and the media used is still books.

Elementary school students certainly don't have much learning experience, so they are unable to find easy ways to understand lessons. Not to mention, delivery by Teachers only rely on the material, making students feel bored, bored, and tend to lack understanding. Especially when it comes to paying attention to lessons, elementary students certainly get bored quickly. According to Adian (2015), there are 4 (four) things that make English teachers less attractive to students, namely making English so difficult and complicated, teachers who are strict, consistently using only one method, and chasing too much material. So, this is what makes it difficult for students to understand the material presented by the teacher.

In elementary schools, the teaching and learning process, especially the introduction of body parts, is still carried out manually and using teaching aids. Seeing this condition, it is necessary to have an alternative, namely in the form of learning media that is able to direct students to positive things, especially recognizing what is inside the student. The body parts introduced to students are the external body parts. Therefore, through this problem, an interactive multimedia-based English learning media facility or application for body parts recognition was created. Using interactive multimedia is the right technology where interactive multimedia is a combination of media in the form of text, images, graphics, sound, animation, video, interaction, etc., and users can freely control the multimedia.

These supporting applications are created based on the applicable curriculum, interesting learning methods, and the characteristics of students so they are able to understand and absorb the information provided by the application. So there are two things that form the problem formulation in this research, the first is, how to design English learning media to introduce body parts to children, especially elementary school children, the next is how to introduce body parts in English to children using interactive multimedia. as the learning media used. It is hoped that this research will be useful both theoretically and practically. For practical benefits, it is hoped that this research can be used as an alternative learning medium for teachers to teach the topic of recognizing body parts in English. Meanwhile, the theoretical benefit is to add references related to interactive multimedia-based English learning media for introducing body parts.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The result of this research is the application of English-based learning media for the introduction of body parts in Class III of Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Al-Ikhlash Jl Semar Saentis, Percut Sei Tuan District, Deli Serdang Regency. Of the class III students, only 45% understood the results of the discussion and 55% only barely understood it. The interest of students who like English is less than students who don't like English.

Instructional Media

Media comes from Latin and is the plural form of medium. It literally means intermediary or introduction. According to Sadiman (2006: 6), the Association of Educational Technology and Communication Technology (Association of Education and Communication Technology) limits media as all forms and channels used to channel messages or information. Learning media can be interpreted as a means used to facilitate teaching and learning activities. In this case, learning media becomes a tool that can help teachers explain lessons to their students. And students are also able to use it in the process of studying material independently.

Furthermore, Gagne in Yusufhadi Miarso (2007: 457) states that learning media are various types of components in the student environment which can stimulate students to learn. Briggs in Miarso (2007: 457) states that learning media is a means of providing stimulation for students to learning process occurs. Apart from that, learning media is also a physical means of conveying learning content/materials such as books, films, videos, and so on. So, from all these opinions, it can be concluded that learning media is anything that can transmit messages, can stimulate the thoughts, feelings and will of students so that it can encourage the creation of a teaching and learning process for students. The types of learning media include Visual Media which can be used in the form of graphs, diagrams, charts, charts, posters, cartoons, comics. Apart from that, there is Audial Media, namely in the form of radio, tape recorders, language laboratories, and the like. The third is Projected Still media: slide: overhead, projector (OHP), in focus and the like. Then the last one is Projected motion media: film, television, video (VCD, DVD, VTR). computers and the like.

All of these media are not very familiar to all teachers and not all of them are able to operate them well. Some of the most familiar media to use are books. It is possible that this is done because this is what is commonly used and is common. In English learning media for the introduction of body parts, projected motion media will be used.

English Learning for Elementary Level

According to (Yudi, 2013) English learning in elementary schools is in principle only an introduction. However, the material taught should be in accordance with the curriculum so that English language learning will be structured systematically starting from class I to class 6. The development of the English language curriculum can be prepared independently in each school according to the conditions of the school, students and their environment. Because this subject is not a mandatory subject, it is recommended to be given to students. So it is not uncommon for some schools to use English as a Local Content (Mulok) subject. To make it easier to learn English for grade 1 elementary school, it is best to first know the national material standards that can be given to students for grade 1 elementary school. As for semester 1 of class 1, students will talk about, alphabet (alphabet), animals (animals), Numbers (numbers), Colors (colors), Part of Body (limbs), My Family (my family), My Home (my house). Meanwhile, for English Class 1 Semester 2 subject matter, namely My Bedroom (my room), My Bathroom (my bathroom), My Kitchen (My Kitchen), My Living Room (My Family Room), Greetings and Partings (greetings and farewells) There are several themes which is almost the same as being repeated in class 2, as for the English lesson material for Class 2 Semester 1, which includes clothes, my family, days of the week (name of the day of the month) and English lesson material for Class 2 Semester 2 namely introduction, part of body, days, school environment and animal. Based on this description, the material taken as a reference for designing this English learning media application is Part of the Body, this material is very easy for elementary school children in grades 1 and 2 to recognize, and this is also the target for users of this learning media.

Multimedia

Etymologically, multimedia comes from the word multi (Latin, noun) which means many, various and medium (Latin) which means something that is used to convey or carry something. (Arsyad 2002), says that media (the plural form of medium), is a word that comes from the Latin medius, which literally means

"middle", 'intermediary', or 'introduction'. The Association of Educational Communication Technology (AECT) states that media is all forms used for the process of distributing information. Rachmat and Alphone, 2005/2006 (as quoted by Wibawa, 2012). The word medium in the American Heritage Dictionary (1991) is also defined as a tool for distributing and presenting information.

Looking at the experts' statements, media can be examples such as films, television, diagrams, printed materials, instructors, computers and others. So multimedia can be defined as media that combines two or more elements consisting of text, images, graphics, photos, audio, video and animation, which have been packaged into digital files (computerized), used to convey messages to the public. As defined Turban and et al (as quoted by Wibawa, 2012), "multimedia is a combination of at least two input and output media. This media can be audio (sound, music), animation, video, text, graphics and images. Examples of Interactive Multimedia are: interactive learning multimedia, game applications. Meanwhile, learning is defined as the process of creating an environment that allows the learning process to occur. So in learning the main thing is how students learn. Learning in the sense of students' mental activity in interacting with the environment which produces relatively constant changes in behavior. Thus, the aspect that is important in learning activities is the environment. How this environment is created by arranging its elements so that it can change student behavior. From the description above, if these two concepts are combined, learning multimedia can be interpreted as multimedia applications used in the learning process, in other words to convey messages (knowledge, skills and attitudes).

Adobe Flash CS6

According to Irfan (2015) Adobe Flash is an application used to design and build presentation devices, publications or other applications that require the availability of means of interaction with its users. Projects built with Flash usually consist of text, images, simple animations, videos and other effects. Several factors support the popularity of Flash as an application for design and animation purposes, including having a vector-based graphic format, small file capacity, having high capabilities in managing program interactivity, having complete facilities for designing and so on. Action Script is a programming language that works on the Adobe Flash Platform. Adobe Action Script was built as a way to develop interactive programming efficiently using the Adobe Flash Action Script Multimedia learning platform ranging from simple to complex animations, use of data, and interactive multimedia learning interfaces in creating English Learning Media applications for Member Introduction This body used action script 3.

CONCLUSION

Recognition of body parts is important for understanding the function and structure of the human body. Through this introduction, we can understand how each part of the body works and interacts to maintain the health and function of the body as a whole.

REFERENFCES

- Ali, M, 2009, "Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Interaktif Kuliah Medan
- Arsyad, A, 2007. Media Pembelajaran, PT Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta.
- Arsyad, A. 2011. Media Pembelajaran. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- Asra M. dan Sumiati, Metode Pembelajaran, Bandung: CV Wacana Prima, 2009.
- Azhar, A. Media Pembelajaran, (Jakarta: Departemen Pendidikan Nasional Direktorat Jendral Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah Direktorat Tenaga Kependidikan, 2003).
- Binanto, I. 2014. Analisa Metode Classic LifeCycle (Waterfall) untuk Pengembangan Perangkat Lunak. Yogyakarta: Teknik Informatika, Universitas Sanata Dharma.
- Chandra. (2006). Action Script Flash MX 2004 untuk Profesional. Palembang: Maxikom.
- Sutopo, A. H., 2003, Multimedia Interaktif dengan Flash, Graha Ilmu, Yogyakarta.
- Irfan, Y. 2015. Manfaat media pembelajaran bagi guru dan siswa.